

Synthesis, Structure and Redox Activity of Cobalt(II)/(III) Complexes of 2-Methoxyazophenols

P. CHATTOPADHYAY, D. K. PAL and C. SINHA*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104

Manuscript received 13 October 1995, accepted 31 January 1996

Co^{II} (2) and Co^{III} (3) complexes of ONO donor tridentate chelates, 2-methoxyazophenols (1) have been synthesised. Their redox activity is critically examined by cyclic voltammetric and coulometric measurements.

The complexes of N, O donor systems continue to attract the attention of many researchers in cobalt chemistry^{1,2}. Amongst the N, O donor ligands, the special emphasis has been placed on Schiff bases in relation to reversible uptake of dioxygen^{3,4}. The N, O chelates in which N and O donor sites are provided by azo and phenolato groups respectively have received little attention. The azophenols are highly useful in a number of biochemical reactions⁴ and analytical chemistry⁵. The *ortho*-substituted azophenols with additional donor groups at the phenyl ring are comparatively less studied in the chemistry of cobalt^{2,6}. Herein we describe synthesis, spectral characterisation and redox activity of cobalt complexes of 2-methoxyazophenols.

- 1
a, R = Me d, R = *t*-Bu
b, R = Cl e, R = 8,9-Benzo
c, R = NO₂

Results and Discussion

The ligands (1) act as tridentate (ONO) donor chelates. The brown red Co^{II} complexes (2) are soluble in chloroform, acetonitrile and pink-red Co^{III} complexes (3) fairly soluble in common organic solvents like methanol, chloroform, acetonitrile. The molar conductance values show that complexes 2 are non-electrolytes and 3 1 : 1 electrolytes. The molecular weights of the four representative complexes (2a, 2d, 3a and 3d : molecular weights : found 531.9, 632.4, 588.7 and 651.9; calculated 540.9, 624.9, 576.4 and 660.4 respectively) support the molecular formula presented in Table 1.

Magnetic study at room temperature indicates high-spin

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES 2 AND 3*

Compd.	Co% Found/ (Calcd.)	E_{M298}^{II} (V)/ (ΔE_p , mV)	E_{L298}^{III} (V)/ (ΔE_p , mV)	μ B.M.	Λ_m $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ mol^{-1}
Co(La) ₂ (2a)	11.12 (10.91)	0.36 (80)	-1.02 (140)	4.78	10.49
Co(Lb) ₂ (2b)	10.31 (10.14)	0.40 (90)	-0.94 (160)	4.62	12.82
Co(Lc) ₂ (2c)	9.90 (9.78)	0.46 (100)	-0.88 (140)	4.70	15.34
Co(Ld) ₂ (2d)	9.59 (9.44)	0.32 (80)	-1.04 (120)	4.84	14.18
Co(Le) ₂ (2e)	9.48 (9.62)	0.40 (80)	-0.94 (120)	4.64	8.54
[Co(La) ₂]Cl (3a)	10.31 (10.23)	—	-0.56 (130)	dia	128.26
[Co(Lb) ₂]Cl (3b)	9.42 (9.55)	—	0.50 (140)	dia	138.48
[Co(Lc) ₂]Cl (3c)	9.09 (9.24)	—	-0.4 (140)	dia	122.62
[Co(Ld) ₂]Cl (3d)	8.81 (8.93)	—	-0.62 (150)	dia	130.59
[Co(Le) ₂]Cl (3e)	8.94 (9.10)	—	-0.52 (130)	dia	140.46

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses and compounds 3 satisfactory Cl analysis also.

nature of the Co^{II}-(2) and Co^{III}-complexes (3) which are diamagnetic. The octahedral Co^{II} can exist in two possible spin states : low-spin with a magnetic moment of 1.8 B.M. and high-spin with 4.2–5.2 B.M.⁷. The observed magnetic moments of Co^{II}-complexes (2) assign high-spin nature of the complexes.

The electronic spectra of complexes 2 reveal bands at 19 445 and a weak band at 16 980 cm^{-1} which are characteristic of Co^{II} in an octahedral surrounding^{7,8}. The bands can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition. The remaining two bands at 28 990 and 40 000 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions respectively, centred primarily on the azo group⁹. Complexes 3 exhibit weak absorption at 15 385 and intense bands 20 000 and

26 667 cm^{-1} . along with the ligand-centred transitions at 29 422 and 40 000 cm^{-1} . The metal-centred transition can be ascribed to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1T_{2g}$ respectively, in octahedral geometry.

The azophenols exhibit medium intense ir band at $\sim 3\ 200\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (O–H of H-bonded phenolic OH)¹⁰ which is absent in the complexes. This indicates coordination of oxygen to the metal centre¹¹. The $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (phenolic) ligand band (1 495–1 520 cm^{-1}) shifts to higher frequency by 30–40 cm^{-1} on coordination with the metal ion¹². The $\nu_{\text{N=N}}$ mode of the free ligand (1 455–1 470 cm^{-1}) is shifted to lower wavenumbers ($\Delta\nu = 80\text{--}90\ \text{cm}^{-1}$) in both the series of complexes, suggesting coordination of the metal ions to azo function¹³. The $\nu_{\text{N=N}}$ band is observed at 1 365–1 385 cm^{-1} for all the complexes. All other ligand bands are slightly blue-shifted in the complexes. In addition to these absorptions, two new bands observed in far-ir region at 520–545 and 345–360 cm^{-1} are assignable⁴ to $\nu_{\text{Co-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Co-N}}$ respectively.

The ${}^1\text{H}$ nmr spectra of the ligands (1) and diamagnetic Co^{III} complexes (3) are recorded in Table 2. The phenolic-OH in 1 resonates at 12.88–15.12 ppm. The disappearance of OH signal in complexes 3 suggests the coordination of phenolic group. The OCH_3 group in complexes is downfield shifted by ~ 0.2 ppm suggesting the coordination to the metal centre fulfilling the octahedral geometry. All other protons are downfield shifted in the complexes by 0.05–0.2 ppm.

Redox activity : Co^{II} complexes 2 are electroactive at the platinum working electrode and display one redox process on the positive side of the SCE and more than one such process on the negative side. Co^{III} complexes 3 exhibit redox responses only on the negative side of the SCE.

The cyclic voltammetric data are collected in Table 1. A reversible $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}/\text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ couple appears around ~ 0.40 V at scan rate 50 mV s^{-1} in acetonitrile. In stirred solution electrolysis freely occurred when the potential was kept fixed on the positive side of the anodic peak and gave coulomb count corresponding to the transfer of $1e/\text{cobalt}$ atom. The formal electrode potential, $E'_{\text{M}298}$ (average of anodic and cathodic peak potentials) movement is in accord with the electronic effect of the substituents in the ligand frame¹⁴. The plot of Hammett σ of substituents¹⁵ against $E'_{\text{M}298}$ is linear and a decrease of the σ -donor capacity of coordinated ligands increases the potential (Fig. 1). The cyclic voltammetric response is thus due to the reversible couple (eqn. 1),

One distinct voltammogram was displayed by both the complexes (2 and 3) in the range -0.4 to -1.2 V. The reduced species does not appear to be enough stable to show the reversibility in few cases and on scan reversal sometimes multiple anodic responses of unclear origin are observed. The quasireversible reduction is due to electron transfer at the azo group (eqn. 2) and in few cases the second peak is observed at high negative potential. The ligand reduction

($E'_{\text{M}298}$) is also plotted against Hammett σ and linearity confirms the potential movement (Fig. 1). The two potentials correlate linearly (figure not shown). A decrease in σ -donor capacity leads to an increase in the effective charge on metal centre, and this in turn stabilises the metal $d\pi$ and ligand- π^* orbitals¹⁴.

 TABLE 2— ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR DATA OF LIGANDS (1) AND COMPLEXES (3)*

Compd. no.	$\delta(\text{J, Hz})$								
	3-H ^a	4,5-H ^b	6-H ^a	8-H ^c	10-H ^b	11-H ^b	Me	OMe	OH
1a	7.04 (8.0)	7.44 (8.0)	7.84 (8.0)	7.76	7.14 (8.4)	6.96 (8.4)	2.32	3.86	13.38
1b	7.05 (8.0)	7.44 (8.0)	7.86 (8.0)	7.89	7.19 (8.0)	6.99 (8.0)	—	3.88	13.84
1c	7.08 (8.0)	7.47 (8.0)	7.90 (8.0)	8.05	7.36 (8.4)	7.04 (8.4)	—	3.94	15.12
1d	7.04 (8.0)	7.44 (8.0)	7.82 (8.0)	7.64	7.06 (8.0)	6.84 (8.0)	1.12 ^d	3.74	12.88
3a	7.20 (8.0)	7.51 (8.0)	8.04 (8.0)	7.84	7.24 (8.0)	7.04 (8.0)	2.42	4.06	—
3b	7.22 (8.0)	7.50 (8.0)	8.08 (8.0)	7.96	7.32 (8.4)	7.11 (8.4)	—	4.08	—
3c	7.25 (8.0)	7.54 (8.0)	8.11 (8.0)	8.18	7.44 (8.0)	7.18 (8.0)	—	4.10	—
3d	7.20 (8.0)	7.52 (8.0)	8.02 (8.0)	7.78	7.18 (8.0)	7.02 (8.0)	1.20 ^d	4.08	—

* CDCl_3 , 100 MHz.

^aDoublet. ^bTriplet. ^cSinglet. ^dt-Butyl group.

Fig. 1 Plot of Hammett σ_p vs $E_{M298}^{O'}$ and $E_{C298}^{O'}$.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. or G.R. (E. Merck) grade. The organic solvents were purified by standard methods. Electrochemically pure acetonitrile and tetraethylammonium perchlorate (TEAP) were prepared by the reported procedure¹⁶.

The elemental analysis was carried out on a Perkin-Elmer 240C analyser. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (CHCl_3) on a Hitachi 330 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Jeol spectrometer (100 MHz). Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a PAR 155 magnetometer and conductance (in acetonitrile) on a Phillips PR 9500 conductivity bridge. Molecular weight was measured with a Knauer vapour pressure osmometer. The electrochemical studies were carried out¹⁹ with the help of a PAR 370-4 electrochemistry system using polarographic analyser (model no. 174A), universal programmer (175), 74 XY recorder (REOO) and cell system (377A). All experiments were performed under a dinitrogen atmosphere in a three-electrode system using planar Beckman 39273 platinum as working electrode. All results were collected at 298 K and referenced to the saturated calomel electrode. The conditions were as follows: scan rate, 50 mV s^{-1} ; solute concn., $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; solvent, acetonitrile; supporting electrolyte, TEAP. For coulometry, a platinum wire-gauge working electrode was used. The reported potentials are uncorrected for junction contributions. Cobalt was estimated by EDTA titration and chloride gravimetrically¹⁷.

The ligands, 2-(methoxy)-2'-hydroxy-5'-substituted-azobenzenes (HL, **1**) were prepared by the reported method¹⁸ by coupling 4-substituted-phenols and diazonium ion obtained from *o*-anisidine. The cobalt(II) complexes (**2**) were synthesised by mixing a methanolic solution (10 ml) of **1a** (0.5 g, 2.07 mmol) with $\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.25 g, 1 mol) under nitrogen in MeOH (10 ml) and refluxing the mixture for 2 h. The brown solids obtained after cooling were washed with cold methanol and dried under reduced pressure (yields 50–65%). The complexes were crystallised from chloroform-methanol (1 : 1, v/v) mixture.

The cobalt(III) complexes (**3**) were synthesised¹⁹ by the oxidation Co^{II} complexes (**2**) as follows. To a solution of **2a** (0.5 g, 0.92 mmol) in chloroform-methanol mixture, Cl_2 -saturated methanol solution was added dropwise with stirring till colour of the solution changed from brown to pink-red; the large excess of Cl_2 -solution was avoided. The mixture was stirred for 1 h and evaporated in air. The solid mass was then washed with water and recrystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture (1 : 1, v/v) to yield **3a**.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. A. Chakravorty, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta, for recording spectra, electrochemical measurements and elemental analyses. Financial assistance from U.G.C., New Delhi (under DSA scheme) is thankfully acknowledged.

References

1. M. B. DAVIES, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **124**, 107.
2. C. H. HOUSECROFT, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **98**, 123; 1988, **90**, 111.
3. T. D. SMITH and J. R. PILBROW, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1981, **39**, 295; A. A. ISSE, A. GENNARD and E. VIANELLO, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 2091.
4. M. S. MASOUD, H. M. ELNAHAS and E. A. KHALIL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 347.
5. S. SHIBATA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1974, **73**, 105.
6. M. S. MASOUD, M. A. S. GOHER and A. M. HEIBA, *Rev. Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **5**, 407; J. ABILDGAARD, P. E. HANSEN, J. JOSEPHSEN and A. LYEKA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1994, **33**, 5271.
7. G. V. BRABHU and D. VENKAPPAYYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **72**, 511.
8. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
9. K. C. KALIA and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **35**, 2231.
10. M. S. MASOUD, A. M. HINDAWY and A. A. SOAYED, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1991, **16**, 372.
11. P. CHATTOPADHYAY and G. SINHA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 76.
12. H. H. FREEDMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **63**, 2900.
13. S. CHATTOPADHYAY, C. SINHA, S. B. CHOWDHURY and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1992, **427**, 111.
14. B. K. GHOSH and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1989, **95**, 239.
15. J. MARCH, "Advanced Organic Chemistry", 3rd ed., Wiley Eastern, New Delhi 1984, p. 244.
16. C. K. PAL, S. CHATTOPADHYAY, C. SINHA and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1994, **33**, 6140.
17. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1961.
18. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1961.
19. R. C. BURROWS and J. C. BAILAR, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 4150.